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Supplementary Table 1. Sample size estimation for the study population

Parameters	Early puberty		Delay puberty	
	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys
Expected incidence in low psychosocial stress exposed (p_0) ^a	14.6% ^[1]	7.5% ^[1]	6.7% ^[2]	3.2% ^[3]
Assumed relative risk of high psychosocial stress exposed (RR) ^b	1.96 ^[4]	2.53 ^[1]	2.32 ^[5]	2.32
Confidence level	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.95
Power	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8
Sample size per group ^c	132	133	195	439
Total sample size (both groups)	264	266	390	878
Total sample size (considering lost to follow-up, 10% increased)	298	293	429	966

^a The incidence of early and delayed puberty timing in girls and boys was derived from previous studies in the general Chinese population. A composite age limits on 3 pubertal signs (breast development, menarche, and pubic hair development for girls, and testicular volume, first spermatorrhea, and pubic hair development for boys) for defining early or delayed puberty established under the “China Puberty Research Collaboration Project” were used to classify early or delayed puberty timing in these studies.

^b Current research has explored fewer sources of stress other than family life, so the RR or OR used for sample size estimation in this study was primarily derived from family-related psychological stress. There is a lack of data on the risk of delayed pubertal in boys exposed to high psychosocial stress, so data from girls was used for sample size estimation.

^c The cohort study sample size estimation formula was used.

$$n = \frac{(z_{\alpha}\sqrt{2pq} + z_{\beta}\sqrt{q_0 + p_1q_1})^2}{(p_1 - p_0)^2}$$

$$p_1 = RR \times p_0, q_0 = 1 - p_0, q_1 = 1 - p_1, q = (q_0 + q_1)/2, p = (p_0 + p_1)/2$$

17 **Supplementary Table 2. Cutoffs of BMI for overweight and obesity among school-**
 18 **age children and adolescents in China** ^a

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Age (year)	BMI for Boy		BMI for Girl	
	overweight	obesity	overweight	obesity
6.0~	16.4	17.7	16.2	17.5
6.5~	16.7	18.1	16.5	18
7.0~	17	18.7	16.8	18.5
7.5~	17.4	19.2	17.2	19
8.0~	17.8	19.7	17.6	19.4
8.5~	18.1	20.3	18.1	19.9
9.0~	18.5	20.8	18.5	20.4
9.5~	18.9	21.4	19	21
10.0~	19.2	21.9	19.5	21.5
10.5~	19.6	22.5	20	22.1
11.0~	19.9	23	20.5	22.7
11.5~	20.3	23.6	21.1	23.3
12.0~	20.7	24.1	21.5	23.9
12.5~	21	24.7	21.9	24.5
13.0~	21.4	25.2	22.2	25
13.5~	21.9	25.7	22.6	25.6
14.0~	22.3	26.1	22.8	25.9
14.5~	22.6	26.4	23	26.3
15.0~	22.9	26.6	23.2	26.6
15.5~	23.1	26.9	23.4	26.9
16.0~	23.3	27.1	23.6	27.1
16.5~	23.5	27.4	23.7	27.4
17.0~	23.7	27.6	23.8	27.6
17.5~	23.8	27.8	23.9	27.8
18.0~	24	28	24	28

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21 ^a According to the screening for overweight and obesity in school-age children and adolescents aged
 22 6–18 years, published by the National Health and Family Planning Commission of the People’s
 23 Republic of China published in 2018 (WS/T 586-2018, China).

24 <http://www.nhc.gov.cn/ewebeditor/uploadfile/2018/03/20180329094554367.pdf>

25 Abbreviations: BMI, body mass index.

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29 **Supplementary Table 3. Scale of Stressful Life Events for Primary School Students**

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31 Dear student,

32 Welcome to take part in our questionnaire survey. Please recall whether you have experienced
 33 any of these life events within six months, and if so, choose the degree of impact of the life events on
 34 you based on your true feelings.

No.	Items	Experienced		Impact on you				
				Minimal impact	A little sad	Quite sad	Very sad	Extremely sad
1	Mom and dad did not live together (divorced or separated)	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
2	Mom and dad had a big quarrel or fight	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
3	Mom and dad was very easy to get angry	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
4	Mom and dad forgot what she (he) had promised me	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
5	Mom and dad criticized me harshly	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
6	Mom and dad beat me	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
7	Mom expected too much from me	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
8	Mom did not allow me to do what I like	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
9	Mom could not meet my demands (wishes)	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
10	The teacher criticized me harshly	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
11	The teacher played favorites with a few of the students	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
12	The teacher didn't praise me even if I do well	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
13	The teacher didn't ask me to help with class affairs, like sending exercise books to classmates	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
14	The teacher said something to me that made me feel sad	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
15	I have so much homework that I can hardly finish it	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
16	I find it difficult to finish my homework	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
17	I didn't do well in the exam and fell behind in the rankings	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
18	I'm late for school	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
19	I'm not as good as the other students at school	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
20	I was bullied and laughed at by other kids	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5

21	I got into arguments and fights with other kids	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
22	The other kids ignored me and didn't play with me	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
23	I was in trouble with my best friend	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
24	Something i love had been lost or broken	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
25	No one helped me when i was in trouble	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
26	I had been misunderstood	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
27	I had to eat a meal that I didn't like	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
28	I couldn't sleep well	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
29	When I was not sleepy, I was forced to sleep	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5
30	I got sick	No	Yes	1	2	3	4	5

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40 **Supplementary Table 4. Internal consistency reliability and Test-retest reliability of**
 41 **SSLEPSS ^a**

Scale Items	Internal consistency reliability (Cronbach α) ^b	Test-retest reliability (ICC) ^c
Total stress	0.89	0.81
Family life	0.78	0.74
Teacher-student relationship	0.74	0.66
Academic adaptation	0.62	0.64
Peer relationship	0.60	0.63
Life adaptation	0.67	0.68

42 ^a In our previous study on the scale development of the Scale of Stressful Life Events for Primary School
 43 Students (SSLEPSS), A total of 1419 students from four primary schools were surveyed to assess the
 44 reliability of the scale. Internal consistency reliability was evaluated using Cronbach's α , while test-retest
 45 reliability was assessed using the intra-class correlation coefficient (ICC) in a subsample of 99 students
 46 after a two-week interval. ^[6].

47 ^b A Cronbach's alpha value above 0.7 is widely considered a measure of acceptable internal consistency of
 48 a scale, and 0.6 is considered for the subscales ^[7].

49 ^c An ICC value less than 0.5 were interpreted as poor reliability, values between 0.5 and 0.75 as moderate
 50 reliability, and values between 0.75 and 0.9 as good reliability ^[8].

51 Abbreviations: SSLEPSS, the Scale of Stressful Life Events for Primary School Students; ICC, intra-class
 52 Correlation Coefficient.

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54 **Supplementary Table 5. The model fit indices for identification the optimal number of trajectories for girls^a**

Psychosocial stress components	Group	B2 (N=433)				Menarche(N=685)				PH2(N=670)				AH2(N=689)			
		BIC	proportion per group>5%	Avepp per group >0.7	E _k	BIC	proportion per group>5%	Avepp per group >0.7	E _k	BIC	proportion per group>5%	Avepp per group >0.7	E _k	BIC	proportion per group>5%	Avepp per group >0.7	E _k
Total	2	-5252.44	Yes	Yes	0.794	-14239.38	Yes	Yes	0.842	-13059.38	Yes	Yes	0.829	-16243.46	Yes	Yes	0.871
	3	-5177.73	Yes	Yes	0.763	-14068.1	Yes	Yes	0.788	-12902.34	Yes	Yes	0.768	-16028	Yes	Yes	0.831
	4	-5163.43	No	Yes	0.749	-14003.28	No	Yes	0.653	-12832.76	No	Yes	0.696	-15932.3	No	Yes	0.759
	5	-5153.24	No	Yes	0.659	-13933.5	No	Yes	0.672	-12804.18	No	Yes	0.769	-15890.92	No	Yes	0.774
Family life	2	-3845.24	Yes	Yes	0.772	-10225.57	Yes	Yes	0.826	-9439.28	Yes	Yes	0.806	-11652.01	Yes	Yes	0.875
	3	-3790.43	Yes	Yes	0.623	-10114.36	Yes	Yes	0.703	-9328.8	Yes	Yes	0.692	-11520.49	Yes	Yes	0.746
	4	-3782.53	No	Yes	0.664	-10091.12	No	Yes	0.744	-9303.57	No	Yes	0.718	-11465.48	No	Yes	0.779
	5	-3790.42	No	No	0.546	-10038.2	No	Yes	0.765	-9252.3	No	Yes	0.736	-11431.66	No	Yes	0.77
Teacher-students relationship	2	-2302.42	Yes	Yes	0.891	-6266.11	Yes	Yes	0.711	-5762.15	Yes	Yes	0.673	-7100.63	Yes	Yes	0.755
	3	-2279.88	Yes	Yes	0.598	-6162.01	Yes	Yes	0.729	-5666.81	Yes	Yes	0.712	-6994.15	Yes	Yes	0.75
	4	-2291.54	No	Yes	0.445	-6146.94	No	Yes	0.777	-5650.53	No	Yes	0.747	-6978.37	No	Yes	0.798
	5	-2301.62	No	No	0.311	-6124.34	No	No	0.744	-5648.41	No	No	0.657	-6952.88	No	No	0.761
Academic adaptation	2	-2967.46	Yes	Yes	0.636	-8156.34	Yes	Yes	0.696	-7490.13	Yes	Yes	0.675	-9384.18	Yes	Yes	0.765
	3	-2941.61	Yes	Yes	0.554	-8057.77	Yes	Yes	0.679	-7408.12	Yes	Yes	0.665	-9268.66	Yes	Yes	0.734
	4	-2943.51	No	Yes	0.59	-8018.63	Yes	Yes	0.712	-7363.4	Yes	Yes	0.689	-9210.64	No	Yes	0.793
	5	-2948.37	No	No	0.544	-8011.72	No	Yes	0.676	-7355.48	No	Yes	0.629	-9195.34	No	Yes	0.775
Peer relationship	2	-3090.32	Yes	Yes	0.734	-8220.07	Yes	Yes	0.703	-7603.02	Yes	Yes	0.728	-9227.46	Yes	Yes	0.742
	3	-3074.32	Yes	Yes	0.544	-8157.95	Yes	Yes	0.655	-7537.91	Yes	Yes	0.644	-9145.59	Yes	Yes	0.704
	4	-3084.82	Yes	No	0.523	-8130.16	Yes	Yes	0.678	-7511.28	Yes	Yes	0.672	-9107.84	No	Yes	0.735
	5	-3087.32	No	Yes	0.61	-8111.92	No	Yes	0.694	-7517.14	No	No	0.659	-9095.43	No	Yes	0.757
Life adaptation	2	-3711.47	Yes	Yes	0.777	-9897.53	Yes	Yes	0.768	-9089.94	Yes	Yes	0.741	-11235.52	Yes	Yes	0.805
	3	-3665.35	Yes	Yes	0.723	-9802.24	Yes	Yes	0.676	-9003.93	Yes	Yes	0.736	-11122.1	Yes	Yes	0.765
	4	-3651.82	No	Yes	0.739	-9768.56	No	Yes	0.741	-8973.31	No	Yes	0.781	-11064.59	No	Yes	0.796
	5	-3651.85	No	Yes	0.722	-9712.68	No	Yes	0.748	-8922.15	No	Yes	0.728	-11002.5	No	Yes	0.782

55 ^a We evaluate the most appropriate number of trajectories based on achieving a relatively low absolute value of BIC without the proportion in each trajectory becoming too low.

56 For girls, we evaluated the optimal model as one that consisted of 3 trajectories.

57 Abbreviations: B2, breast development tanner II; PH2, pubic hair development tanner II; AH2, axillary hair development tanner II; BIC, Bayesian Information Criteria; Avepp,

58 average posterior probability; E_k, relative entropy.

59 **Supplementary Table 6. The model fit indices for identification the optimal number of trajectories for boys^a**

Psychosocial stress components	Group	T2 (N=577)				FS (N=652)				PH2 (N=658)				AH2 (N=684)			
		BIC	proportion per group >5%	Avepp per group >0.7	E _k	BIC	proportion per group >5%	Avepp per group >0.7	E _k	BIC	proportion per group >5%	Avepp per group >0.7	E _k	BIC	proportion per group >5%	Avepp per group >0.7	E _k
Total	2	-12238.59	Yes	Yes	0.811	-15380.71	Yes	Yes	0.861	-14881.67	Yes	Yes	0.859	-17308.34	Yes	Yes	0.878
	3	-12093.33	Yes	Yes	0.827	-15187.48	Yes	Yes	0.859	-14698.76	Yes	Yes	0.851	-17066.61	Yes	Yes	0.864
	4	-12033.3	No	Yes	0.778	-15120.4	No	Yes	0.835	-14637.04	No	Yes	0.836	-17000.96	No	Yes	0.83
	5	-12008.41	No	Yes	0.772	-15096.76	No	Yes	0.758	-14618.02	No	Yes	0.73	-16962.03	No	Yes	0.784
Family life	2	-9116.08	Yes	Yes	0.789	-11435.09	Yes	Yes	0.832	-11069.75	Yes	Yes	0.82	-12797.58	Yes	Yes	0.853
	3	-9046.63	Yes	Yes	0.762	-11336.85	Yes	Yes	0.799	-10977.89	Yes	Yes	0.798	-12676.93	Yes	Yes	0.799
	4	-9006.92	No	Yes	0.728	-11284.96	No	Yes	0.747	-10929.5	No	Yes	0.746	-12615.04	No	Yes	0.768
	5	-8999.02	No	Yes	0.734	-11262.78	No	Yes	0.731	-10914.27	No	Yes	0.732	-12595.39	No	Yes	0.752
Teacher-students relationship	2	-5735.08	Yes	Yes	0.708	-7185.73	Yes	Yes	0.72	-6989.8	Yes	Yes	0.763	-8115.94	Yes	Yes	0.744
	3	-5669.79	Yes	Yes	0.667	-7093.93	Yes	Yes	0.715	-6899.49	Yes	Yes	0.703	-7990.5	Yes	Yes	0.761
	4	-5634.12	No	Yes	0.73	-7051.77	No	Yes	0.771	-6861.26	No	Yes	0.762	-7945.87	No	Yes	0.81
	5	-5637.38	No	No	0.64	-7048.02	No	No	0.738	-6843.96	No	No	0.794	-7928.66	No	No	0.818
Academic adaptation	2	-7101.9	Yes	Yes	0.658	-8934.11	Yes	Yes	0.736	-8656.76	Yes	Yes	0.727	-10112.8	Yes	Yes	0.765
	3	-7019.27	Yes	Yes	0.708	-8813.19	Yes	Yes	0.75	-8546.63	Yes	Yes	0.737	-9971.17	Yes	Yes	0.774
	4	-7008.6	No	Yes	0.689	-8789.61	No	Yes	0.743	-8523.87	No	Yes	0.74	-9934.73	No	Yes	0.787
	5	-7000.83	No	Yes	0.703	-8786.52	No	Yes	0.758	-8520.15	No	Yes	0.755	-9923.71	No	Yes	0.733
Peer relationship	2	-6706.13	Yes	Yes	0.715	-8327.66	Yes	Yes	0.755	-8121.78	Yes	Yes	0.739	-9333.06	Yes	Yes	0.77
	3	-6626.15	Yes	Yes	0.693	-8225.31	Yes	Yes	0.734	-8007.76	Yes	Yes	0.75	-9181.1	Yes	Yes	0.777
	4	-6613.2	No	Yes	0.684	-8203.13	No	Yes	0.728	-7989.22	No	Yes	0.708	-9150.04	No	Yes	0.807
	5	-6617.17	No	Yes	0.703	-8187.36	No	Yes	0.771	-7972.74	No	Yes	0.758	-9132.15	No	Yes	0.802
Life adaptation	2	-8554.73	Yes	Yes	0.755	-10643.69	Yes	Yes	0.819	-10315	Yes	Yes	0.819	-11907.04	Yes	Yes	0.846
	3	-8491.98	Yes	Yes	0.718	-10552.04	Yes	Yes	0.783	-10238.5	Yes	Yes	0.758	-11806.57	Yes	Yes	0.77
	4	-8474.1	No	Yes	0.683	-10517.25	No	Yes	0.749	-10211.11	No	Yes	0.717	-11758.54	No	Yes	0.759
	5	-8456.95	No	Yes	0.728	-10509.92	No	Yes	0.785	-10203.95	No	Yes	0.755	-11733.39	No	Yes	0.778

60 ^a We evaluate the most appropriate number of trajectories based on achieving a relatively low absolute value of BIC without the proportion in each trajectory becoming too low.

61 For boys, we evaluated the optimal model as one that consisted of 3 trajectories.

62 Abbreviations: Tvol4, testicular volume ≥ 4 ml; FS, first spermatorrhea; PH2, pubic hair development tanner II; AH2, axillary hair development tanner II; BIC, Bayesian

63 Information Criteria; Avepp, average posterior probability; E_k, relative entropy.

Supplementary Table 7. The average value of the total score of psychosocial stress by onset statuses of pubertal outcomes for girls at each survey ^{ab}

Survey	B2				Menarche				PH2				AH2			
	Onset		Not yet		Onset		Not yet		Onset		Not yet		Onset		Not yet	
	No.	Average value	No.	Average value	No.	Average value	No.	Average value	No.	Average value	No.	Average value	No.	Average value	No.	Average value
1	289	23.00 (12.00-39.00)	443	20.00 (12.00-37.00)	47	32.00 (18.00-41.00)	685	21.00 (12.00-37.00)	62	25.00 (15.00-41.00)	670	21.00 (12.00-37.00)	43	31.00 (19.00-42.00)	689	21.00 (12.00-37.00)
2	409	22.00 (12.50-38.50)	323	20.50 (13.00-33.50)	91	25.50 (15.50-40.00)	641	20.50 (12.00-35.00)	133	21.00 (13.00-38.00)	599	21.00 (13.00-35.50)	63	27.00 (15.50-41.50)	669	20.50 (12.00-35.50)
3	525	21.33 (12.33-37.00)	207	21.00 (13.33-32.33)	133	22.33 (12.67-38.33)	599	20.67 (12.33-34.00)	175	22.00 (12.33-37.67)	557	21.00 (12.33-34.00)	83	24.67 (14.67-40.00)	649	21.00 (12.00-34.00)
4	571	21.25 (12.50-36.25)	161	20.00 (13.00-32.50)	222	21.00 (12.33-36.33)	510	21.00 (12.75-33.50)	232	22.50 (13.63-37.00)	500	20.38 (12.25-32.50)	127	25.00 (15.75-39.33)	605	20.25 (12.25-33.00)
5	640	21.00 (12.90-35.30)	92	19.00 (10.70-28.80)	267	21.33 (13.60-35.67)	465	20.60 (12.60-32.40)	316	21.00 (13.15-35.83)	416	20.80 (12.60-31.90)	169	21.80 (14.40-36.00)	563	20.60 (12.20-32.40)
6	691	21.67 (12.67-34.00)	41	16.67 (10.00-28.50)	358	22.00 (13.33-35.00)	374	20.20 (12.00-31.50)	428	20.83 (12.17-34.50)	304	22.42 (12.83-31.92)	233	22.00 (13.83-34.33)	499	21.00 (11.83-33.00)
7	709	21.00(12.29-32.29)	23	19.71 (12.25-26.50)	439	21.00 (12.29-32.17)	293	20.50 (11.86-31.86)	515	20.14 (12.00-32.14)	217	22.71 (12.57-32.00)	298	19.79 (12.43-32.00)	434	21.62 (11.71-32.14)
8	717	20.86 (12.29-32.17)	15	17.86 (13.29-26.50)	504	20.79 (12.29-32.15)	228	21.14 (11.79-32.00)	565	20.57 (12.29-32.17)	167	22.00 (12.29-31.86)	380	19.64 (12.14-32.00)	352	22.00 (12.29-32.29)
9	718	20.93 (12.29-32.17)	14	16.50 (13.29-26.50)	561	20.71 (12.29-32.17)	171	21.29 (11.86-31.86)	622	20.62 (12.40-32.29)	110	21.79 (11.00-31.71)	447	20.43 (12.40-32.00)	285	21.57 (11.71-32.43)
10	719	20.86 (12.29-32.17)	13	17.86 (14.00-26.50)	595	20.86 (12.29-32.33)	137	21.00 (12.25-31.57)	643	20.57 (12.29-32.17)	89	22.00(11.00-31.71)	496	20.15 (12.41-32.17)	236	21.83 (11.62-31.93)
11	719	20.86 (12.29-32.17)	13	17.86 (14.00-26.50)	604	20.69 (12.29-32.31)	128	21.43 (12.05-31.57)	643	20.57 (12.29-32.17)	89	22.00 (11.00-31.71)	498	20.30 (12.43-32.17)	234	21.62 (11.57-31.86)
12	719	20.86 (12.29-32.17)	13	17.86 (14.00-26.50)	608	20.69 (12.29-32.38)	124	21.43 (12.05-31.21)	648	20.62 (12.29-32.17)	84	22.00 (11.10-31.79)	531	20.17 (12.29-32.43)	201	21.67 (11.67-31.43)
13	719	20.86 (12.29-32.17)	13	17.86 (14.00-26.50)	610	20.69 (12.29-32.33)	122	21.43 (11.86-31.43)	651	20.57 (12.29-32.17)	81	22.00 (11.71-31.86)	540	20.30 (12.29-32.43)	192	21.62 (11.69-31.21)
14	719	20.86 (12.29-32.17)	13	17.86 (14.00-26.50)	612	20.79 (12.29-32.31)	120	21.14 (11.79-31.57)	651	20.57 (12.29-32.17)	81	22.00 (11.71-31.86)	548	20.30 (12.29-32.43)	184	21.83 (11.79-31.21)
15	719	20.86 (12.29-32.17)	13	17.86 (14.00-26.50)	612	20.79 (12.29-32.31)	120	21.14 (11.79-31.57)	651	20.57 (12.29-32.17)	81	22.00 (11.71-31.86)	552	20.15 (12.29-32.38)	180	22.00 (12.27-31.57)

^a The average value of the total score of psychosocial stress for each subjects was calculated using the current and all previous survey assessments.

^b Data are median (Interquartile range).

Abbreviations: B2, breast development tanner II; PH2, pubic hair development tanner II; AH2, axillary hair development tanner II.

Supplementary Table 8. The average value of the total score of psychosocial stress by onset statuses of pubertal outcomes for boys at each survey ^{ab}

Survey	Tvol4				FS				PH2				AH2			
	Onset		Not yet		Onset		Not yet		Onset		Not yet		Onset		Not yet	
	No.	Average value	No.	Average value	No.	Average value	No.	Average value	No.	Average value	No.	Average value	No.	Average value	No.	Average value
1	111	18.50 (11.00-32.00)	577	22.00 (11.00-36.00)	36	27.50 (12.00-46.00)	652	22.00 (11.00-35.00)	30	18.00 (11.00-49.00)	658	22.00 (11.00-35.00)	4	7.00 (1.00-32.50)	684	22.00 (11.00-35.00)
2	156	19.00 (10.00-33.00)	532	23.50 (13.50-35.50)	53	19.50 (10.50-40.50)	635	22.00 (12.50-35.50)	37	17.50 (10.00-30.00)	651	22.50 (12.50-35.50)	6	30.75 (7.50-51.50)	682	22.00 (12.50-35.50)
3	191	18.00 (10.00-31.33)	497	23.00 (13.33-35.00)	72	14.83 (8.83-32.67)	616	22.17 (12.50-34.83)	66	14.50 (7.33-28.00)	622	22.67 (12.67-35.00)	6	28.00 (5.33-50.00)	682	21.50 (12.00-34.33)
4	260	18.29 (10.00-31.00)	428	22.75 (12.75-35.63)	117	18.33 (9.00-30.33)	571	22.00 (12.00-34.50)	141	15.00 (8.67-28.67)	547	22.75 (12.50-35.50)	59	14.00 (7.00-30.67)	629	22.00 (11.75-34.25)
5	289	18.40 (10.20-31.00)	399	22.20 (12.33-34.80)	120	19.32 (10.53-30.23)	568	21.17 (11.20-34.30)	189	17.80 (10.40-27.40)	499	22.40 (11.40-35.40)	31	16.50 (10.75-26.40)	657	21.00 (11.20-33.80)
6	346	18.42 (10.33-32.50)	342	22.33 (13.00-35.00)	163	19.60 (11.25-33.50)	525	20.83 (12.00-33.67)	224	18.33 (10.33-30.79)	464	21.75 (12.33-35.08)	40	18.33 (11.83-25.58)	648	21.08 (11.67-33.71)
7	396	18.37 (10.57-30.75)	292	21.27 (12.14-34.64)	222	18.21 (10.57-29.80)	466	20.93 (11.57-34.14)	288	18.29 (10.54-29.92)	400	20.93 (11.57-35.00)	102	16.43 (10.43-23.86)	586	20.64 (11.43-34.00)
8	466	18.57 (10.67-30.83)	222	21.57 (12.33-34.71)	267	18.33 (10.50-30.43)	421	20.86 (11.57-34.14)	355	18.29 (10.67-30.14)	333	21.33 (11.57-35.14)	150	17.29 (9.86-25.57)	538	20.86 (11.57-34.14)
9	509	19.17 (10.71-30.67)	179	21.33 (12.43-35.29)	317	18.86 (10.57-31.17)	371	20.57 (11.57-33.43)	410	18.31 (10.83-30.29)	278	22.14 (12.00-35.29)	205	17.14 (10.50-26.57)	483	21.14 (11.57-35.00)
10	543	19.00 (10.71-30.57)	145	22.71 (13.71-35.71)	369	18.57 (10.71-30.57)	319	21.00 (11.57-35.00)	480	18.57 (11.07-30.14)	208	22.79 (12.00-35.93)	269	17.57 (10.57-27.71)	419	21.14 (12.00-34.71)
11	544	18.93 (10.77-30.57)	144	22.71 (13.64-36.00)	387	18.57 (10.83-30.57)	301	21.14 (11.57-35.00)	487	18.57 (11.14-30.29)	201	22.86 (12.00-35.86)	282	17.62 (10.43-27.71)	406	21.31 (12.14-35.00)
12	581	19.17 (11.14-31.00)	107	21.57 (13.36-33.00)	426	19.00 (11.14-30.86)	262	21.14 (11.43-35.00)	521	19.00 (11.29-30.57)	167	23.20 (11.57-37.14)	354	18.29 (10.67-29.83)	334	21.45 (12.00-35.29)
13	590	19.23 (11.00-31.17)	98	22.24 (13.71-36.43)	462	19.17 (11.14-31.17)	226	21.14 (11.43-35.00)	533	19.00 (11.29-30.67)	155	23.20 (11.57-37.14)	396	18.50 (10.69-30.21)	292	21.45 (12.14-35.29)
14	591	19.29 (11.00-31.17)	97	22.20 (13.71-36.43)	469	19.14 (11.14-31.00)	219	21.33 (11.57-35.00)	538	19.00 (11.29-30.86)	150	22.96 (11.57-36.43)	414	18.57 (10.83-30.29)	274	21.27 (12.00-35.29)
15	591	19.29 (11.00-31.17)	97	22.20 (13.71-36.43)	471	19.14 (11.14-31.00)	217	21.33 (11.57-35.00)	540	19.00 (11.23-30.85)	148	23.43 (11.64-36.79)	421	18.86 (11.14-30.43)	267	21.14 (12.00-35.29)

^a The average value of the total score of psychosocial stress for each subjects was calculated using the current and all previous survey assessments.

^b Data are median (Interquartile range).

Abbreviations: Tvol4, testicular volume ≥ 4 ml; FS, first spermatorrhea; PH2, pubic hair development tanner II.

Supplementary Table 9. The characteristics of the included girls for each pubertal outcome by total score of PS trajectories ^a

Variables	B2 (N=443)			P	Menarche (N=685)			P	PH2 (N=670)			P	AH2 (N=689)			P
	Low, gradual decline TPS trajectory (n=267)	Moderate, gradual decline TPS trajectory (n=148)	High, rise then decline TPS trajectory (n=28)		Low, gradual decline TPS trajectory (n=387)	Moderate, gradual declined TPS trajectory (n=227)	High, rise then decline TPS trajectory (n=71)		Low, gradual decline TPS trajectory (n=378)	Moderate, gradual declined TPS trajectory (n=231)	High, rise then decline TPS trajectory (n=61)		Low, gradual decline TPS trajectory (n=387)	Moderate, gradual declined TPS trajectory (n=236)	High, rise then decline TPS trajectory (n=66)	
Child Characteristics																
Age at survey 1	9.19±0.94	9.17±1	9.47±1.02	0.31	9.67±1.08	9.57±1.15	9.73±1.17	0.46	9.65±1.06	9.52±1.14	9.64±1.11	0.36	9.72±1.09	9.54±1.15	9.68±1.14	0.15
BMI at survey 1				0.54				0.41				0.63				0.4
Normal	229 (85.77)	125 (84.46)	27 (96.43)		323 (83.46)	191 (84.14)	65 (91.55)		321 (84.92)	190 (82.25)	55 (90.16)		320 (82.69)	196 (83.05)	60 (90.91)	
Overweight	23 (8.61)	13 (8.78)	1 (3.57)		35 (9.04)	23 (10.13)	3 (4.23)		34 (8.99)	24 (10.39)	3 (4.92)		38 (9.82)	25 (10.59)	2 (3.03)	
Obesity	15 (5.62)	10 (6.76)	0 (0)		29 (7.49)	13 (5.73)	3 (4.23)		23 (6.08)	17 (7.36)	3 (4.92)		29 (7.49)	15 (6.36)	4 (6.06)	
Birth weight (g)	3.26±0.43	3.19±0.49	3.31±0.57	0.29	3.24±0.47	3.19±0.49	3.31±0.61	0.24	3.24±0.47	3.20±0.48	3.33±0.60	0.16	3.25±0.46	3.22±0.47	3.28±0.61	0.61
Breastfeeding in first 6 months				0.73				0.93				0.83				0.89
Exclusive breastfeeding	161 (61.69)	101 (68.24)	17 (60.71)		240 (63.49)	151 (66.52)	48 (67.61)		243 (65.85)	152 (65.8)	40 (65.57)		242 (64.02)	160 (67.8)	43 (65.15)	
Formula feeding	51 (19.54)	24 (16.22)	5 (17.86)		66 (17.46)	35 (15.42)	11 (15.49)		61 (16.53)	34 (14.72)	12 (19.67)		63 (16.67)	36 (15.25)	12 (18.18)	
Mixed feeding	49 (18.77)	23 (15.54)	6 (21.43)		72 (19.05)	41 (18.06)	12 (16.9)		65 (17.62)	45 (19.48)	9 (14.75)		73 (19.31)	40 (16.95)	11 (16.67)	
Maternal/Paternal Characteristics																
Education level of father				0.94				0.16				0.58				0.51
Primary school or lower	120 (44.94)	73 (49.32)	13 (46.43)		173 (44.7)	112 (49.34)	33 (46.48)		171 (45.24)	111 (48.05)	30 (49.18)		175 (45.22)	114 (48.31)	30 (45.45)	
Middle school	83 (31.09)	43 (29.05)	9 (32.14)		115 (29.72)	77 (33.92)	21 (29.58)		116 (30.69)	77 (33.33)	17 (27.87)		118 (30.49)	79 (33.47)	20 (30.3)	
College or higher	64 (23.97)	32 (21.62)	6 (21.43)		99 (25.58)	38 (16.74)	17 (23.94)		91 (24.07)	43 (18.61)	14 (22.95)		94 (24.29)	43 (18.22)	16 (24.24)	
Education level of mother				0.79				0.09				0.19				0.23
Primary school or lower	120 (45.11)	74 (50)	15 (53.57)		172 (44.56)	126 (55.51)	35 (49.3)		171 (45.36)	128 (55.41)	30 (49.18)		175 (45.34)	128 (54.24)	31 (46.97)	
Middle school	82 (30.83)	44 (29.73)	8 (28.57)		129 (33.42)	67 (29.52)	21 (29.58)		127 (33.69)	67 (29)	19 (31.15)		130 (33.68)	71 (30.08)	20 (30.3)	
College or higher	64 (24.06)	30 (20.27)	5 (17.86)		85 (22.02)	34 (14.98)	15 (21.13)		79 (20.95)	36 (15.58)	12 (19.67)		81 (20.98)	37 (15.68)	15 (22.73)	
Average monthly household income (RMB)				0.5				0.37				0.63				0.22
<2000	78 (29.21)	53 (36.05)	7 (25)		109 (28.24)	81 (35.68)	20 (28.57)		110 (29.18)	81 (35.06)	19 (31.67)		106 (27.46)	86 (36.44)	22 (33.85)	
2001-4000	119 (44.57)	55 (37.41)	14 (50)		176 (45.6)	97 (42.73)	33 (47.14)		173 (45.89)	96 (41.56)	28 (46.67)		182 (47.15)	96 (40.68)	28 (43.08)	
>4000	70 (26.22)	39 (26.53)	7 (25)		101 (26.17)	49 (21.59)	17 (24.29)		94 (24.93)	54 (23.38)	13 (21.67)		98 (25.39)	54 (22.88)	15 (23.08)	
Maternal emotion during pregnancy				0.61				0.31				0.64				0.25
Good mood	173 (66.03)	98 (66.67)	16 (57.14)		260 (68.78)	146 (64.6)	43 (60.56)		252 (68.11)	152 (66.09)	38 (62.3)		261 (69.05)	154 (65.53)	39 (59.09)	
Low mood	89 (33.97)	49 (33.33)	12 (42.86)		118 (31.22)	80 (35.4)	28 (39.44)		118 (31.89)	78 (33.91)	23 (37.7)		117 (30.95)	81 (34.47)	27 (40.91)	
Maternal menarche age	13.71±1.48	13.89±1.48	13.86±1.43	0.5	13.62±1.41	13.85±1.52	13.84±1.34	0.14	13.6±1.41	13.89±1.56	13.8±1.3	0.06	13.6±1.44	13.81±1.52	13.91±1.31	0.1

^a Data are mean ± SD, n (%)

Abbreviations: B2, breast development tanner II; PH2, pubic hair development tanner II; AH2, axillary hair development tanner II; TPS, total score of psychosocial stress; BMI, body mass index.

Supplementary Table 10. The characteristics of the included boys for each pubertal outcome by total score of PS trajectories ^a

Variables	Tvol4 (N=577)			P	FS (N=652)			P	PH2 (N=658)			P	AH2 (N=684)			P
	Low, gradual decline TPS trajectory (n=344)	Moderate, gradual declined TPS trajectory (n=189)	High, gradual rise TPS trajectory (n=44)		Low, gradual decline TPS trajectory (n=392)	Moderate, gradual declined TPS trajectory (n=205)	High, stable TPS trajectory (n=55)		Low, gradual decline TPS trajectory (n=390)	Moderate, gradual declined TPS trajectory (n=212)	High, stable TPS trajectory (n=56)		Low, gradual decline TPS trajectory (n=395)	Moderate, gradual declined TPS trajectory (n=227)	High, stable TPS trajectory (n=62)	
Child Characteristics																
Age at survey 1	9.19±0.94	9.17±1	9.47±1.02	0.18	9.67±1.08	9.57±1.15	9.73±1.17	0.26	9.65±1.06	9.52±1.14	9.64±1.11	0.04	9.72±1.09	9.54±1.15	9.68±1.14	0.12
BMI at survey 1				0.57				0.04				0.09				0.08
Normal	260 (76.02)	153 (80.95)	35 (79.55)		282 (72.12)	168 (81.95)	47 (85.45)		282 (72.68)	171 (80.66)	48 (85.71)		286 (72.59)	183 (80.97)	52 (83.87)	
Overweight	37 (10.82)	19 (10.05)	3 (6.82)		54 (13.81)	19 (9.27)	4 (7.27)		51 (13.14)	22 (10.38)	4 (7.14)		52 (13.2)	23 (10.18)	6 (9.68)	
Obesity	45 (13.16)	17 (8.99)	6 (13.64)		55 (14.07)	18 (8.78)	4 (7.27)		55 (14.18)	19 (8.96)	4 (7.14)		56 (14.21)	20 (8.85)	4 (6.45)	
Birth weight (g)	3.26±0.43	3.20±0.48	3.31±0.57	0.9	3.24±0.47	3.20±0.49	3.30±0.61	0.43	3.24±0.47	3.20±0.49	3.33±0.60	0.5	3.24±0.46	3.22±0.47	3.28±0.62	0.51
Breastfeeding in first 6 months				0.68				0.54				0.64				0.64
Exclusive breastfeeding	214 (62.76)	126 (68.11)	29 (69.05)		244 (62.72)	137 (67.82)	38 (73.08)		244 (63.05)	140 (67.31)	39 (72.22)		245 (62.66)	152 (67.86)	41 (69.49)	
Formula feeding	59 (17.3)	30 (16.22)	7 (16.67)		71 (18.25)	32 (15.84)	7 (13.46)		69 (17.83)	32 (15.38)	8 (14.81)		71 (18.16)	36 (16.07)	10 (16.95)	
Mixed feeding	68 (19.94)	29 (15.68)	6 (14.29)		74 (19.02)	33 (16.34)	7 (13.46)		74 (19.12)	36 (17.31)	7 (12.96)		75 (19.18)	36 (16.07)	8 (13.56)	
Maternal/Paternal Characteristics																
Education level of father				0.07				0.02				0.04				0.01
Primary school or lower	138 (40.12)	99 (52.38)	16 (36.36)		157 (40.26)	111 (54.15)	21 (38.18)		160 (41.24)	114 (53.77)	21 (37.5)		160 (40.71)	124 (54.63)	23 (37.1)	
Middle school	131 (38.08)	59 (31.22)	18 (40.91)		148 (37.95)	60 (29.27)	19 (34.55)		148 (38.14)	62 (29.25)	22 (39.29)		150 (38.17)	65 (28.63)	22 (35.48)	
College or higher	75 (21.8)	31 (16.4)	10 (22.73)		85 (21.79)	34 (16.59)	15 (27.27)		80 (20.62)	36 (16.98)	13 (23.21)		83 (21.12)	38 (16.74)	17 (27.42)	
Education level of mother				0.36				0.48				0.3				0.17
Primary school or lower	156 (45.75)	101 (53.72)	19 (43.18)		180 (46.27)	105 (51.47)	26 (47.27)		183 (47.29)	112 (53.08)	25 (44.64)		183 (46.68)	120 (53.1)	27 (43.55)	
Middle school	120 (35.19)	55 (29.26)	14 (31.82)		140 (35.99)	61 (29.9)	16 (29.09)		139 (35.92)	58 (27.49)	20 (35.71)		144 (36.73)	64 (28.32)	20 (32.26)	
College or higher	65 (19.06)	32 (17.02)	11 (25)		69 (17.74)	38 (18.63)	13 (23.64)		65 (16.8)	41 (19.43)	11 (19.64)		65 (16.58)	42 (18.58)	15 (24.19)	
Average monthly household income (RMB)				0.36				0.44				0.66				0.83
<2000	101 (29.36)	65 (34.39)	11 (25)		113 (28.83)	69 (33.66)	18 (32.73)		114 (29.23)	71 (33.49)	15 (26.79)		114 (28.86)	75 (33.04)	20 (32.26)	
2001-4000	155 (45.06)	84 (44.44)	25 (56.82)		178 (45.41)	91 (44.39)	28 (50.91)		180 (46.15)	97 (45.75)	29 (51.79)		184 (46.58)	101 (44.49)	29 (46.77)	
>4000	88 (25.58)	40 (21.16)	8 (18.18)		101 (25.77)	45 (21.95)	9 (16.36)		96 (24.62)	44 (20.75)	12 (21.43)		97 (24.56)	51 (22.47)	13 (20.97)	
Maternal emotion during pregnancy				0.54				0.43				0.32				0.23
Good mood	229 (67.16)	116 (62.37)	28 (66.67)		255 (65.55)	123 (60.59)	35 (67.31)		261 (67.44)	128 (61.24)	35 (64.81)		261 (66.75)	135 (60)	39 (66.1)	
Low mood	112 (32.84)	70 (37.63)	14 (33.33)		134 (34.45)	80 (39.41)	17 (32.69)		126 (32.56)	81 (38.76)	19 (35.19)		130 (33.25)	90 (40)	20 (33.9)	
Maternal menarche age	13.71±1.48	13.89±1.48	13.86±1.43	0.85	13.62±1.41	13.85±1.52	13.84±1.34	0.63	13.6±1.41	13.89±1.56	13.8±1.3	0.92	13.6±1.44	13.81±1.52	13.91±1.31	0.35

^a Data are mean ± SD, n (%)

Abbreviations: Tvol4, testicular volume ≥ 4 ml; FS, first spermatorrhea; PH2, pubic hair development tanner II; TPS, total score of psychosocial stress; BMI, body mass index.

Supplementary Table 11. The average value of the total score and the 5 components score of psychosocial stress by trajectories for each pubertal outcome of girls

Psychosocial stress	B2 (N=443)		Menarche (N=685)		P2 (N=670)		A2 (N=689)	
	Trajectory group	Average value	Trajectory group	Average value	Trajectory group	Average value	Trajectory group	Average value
Total	All	20 (12.33-34)	All	19.71 (11.33-31.86)	All	20 (11.29-31.43)	All	19.29 (11-30.8)
	Low, gradual decline	14 (8.5-18.4)	Low, gradual decline	12.33 (7.67-17)	Low, gradual decline	12.27 (7.57-17)	Low, gradual decline	11.71 (7.33-15.71)
	Moderate, gradual decline	35.5 (29.7-43)	Moderate, gradual decline	31 (26.29-37)	Moderate, gradual decline	30.67 (26.43-38.5)	Moderate, gradual decline	29 (24.14-34.62)
	High, rise then decline	65 (59.67-71.25)	High, rise then decline	54.4 (48.5-59.57)	High, rise then decline	55.5 (50.25-63)	High, rise then decline	54.61 (48.71-62.83)
Family life	All	6.5 (2.75-11)	All	6 (2.67-10.5)	All	6 (2.6-10.4)	All	5.43 (2.57-9.57)
	Low, gradual decline	2 (0.92-3)	Low, gradual decline	1.43 (0.71-2.43)	Low, gradual decline	2 (0.8-2.75)	Low, gradual decline	1.4 (0.71-2.29)
	Moderate, gradual decline	9 (6.67-11.5)	Moderate, gradual decline	6.57 (4.43-8.83)	Moderate, gradual decline	7.6 (5.6-10)	Moderate, gradual decline	6.29 (4.25-8.33)
	High, rise then decline	21 (19-24.2)	High, rise then decline	16.64 (14-19.46)	High, rise then decline	18.07 (15.5-21)	High, rise then decline	16 (13.71-19.4)
Teacher-students relationship	All	1 (0-2.5)	All	1 (0.29-2.6)	All	1 (0.25-2.6)	All	1.14 (0.29-2.57)
	Low, gradual decline	0 (0-0)	Low, gradual decline	0.14 (0-0.43)	Low, gradual decline	0 (0-0.43)	Low, gradual decline	0.25 (0-0.5)
	Moderate, stable	2 (1-3.2)	Moderate, stable	2 (1.31-3.17)	Moderate, stable	2 (1.25-3.08)	Moderate, stable	2 (1.29-3)
	High, rise then decline	10 (8.17-11.5)	High, rise then decline	7.45 (6.29-9.8)	High, rise then decline	7.45 (6.33-10.14)	High, rise then decline	6.71 (6-8.67)
Academic adaptation	All	2.5 (1-5)	All	3 (1.25-5.5)	All	2.85 (1.2-5.5)	All	2.86 (1.25-5.5)
	Low, gradual decline	0.24 (0-0.75)	Low, gradual decline	0.71 (0.29-1.29)	Low, gradual decline	0.57 (0.15-1.27)	Low, gradual decline	0.86 (0.33-1.43)
	Moderate, stable	3.33 (2-5)	Moderate, stable	3.67 (2.5-4.93)	Moderate, stable	3.59 (2.43-5)	Moderate, stable	3.71 (2.57-5.25)
	High, rise and decline	10 (8.38-12.67)	High, rise and decline	9.14 (7.86-11)	High, rise and decline	9.54 (8.14-12.07)	High, rise and decline	9.29 (8-11.4)
Peer relationship	All	3 (1.4-5.33)	All	2.83 (1.33-5)	All	3 (1.29-5.14)	All	2.71 (1.29-4.86)
	Low, gradual decline	0 (0-1)	Low, gradual decline	1 (0.5-1.67)	Low, gradual decline	1 (0.4-1.57)	Low, gradual decline	1 (0.57-1.71)
	Moderate, gradual decline	3.77 (2.25-5.25)	Moderate, gradual decline	4 (3-5.43)	Moderate, gradual decline	4 (2.75-5.29)	Moderate, gradual decline	3.85 (2.86-5.29)
	High, rise then decline	11.4 (9.6-15.75)	High, rise then decline	9.8 (8.73-12.37)	High, rise then decline	10.43 (9-12.4)	High, rise then decline	9.5 (8.57-11.17)
Life adaptation	All	6.5 (3.33-10)	All	5.67 (3.14-9)	All	5.59 (3.25-9.17)	All	5.43 (3-8.43)
	Low, gradual decline	0.82 (0.21-1.27)	Low, gradual decline	2.59 (1.71-3.67)	Low, gradual decline	3.8 (2.15-5)	Low, gradual decline	3 (1.86-4.43)
	Moderate, gradual decline	6.4 (4-8.5)	Moderate, gradual decline	7.27 (6-9.4)	Moderate, gradual decline	9.85 (7.59-12)	Moderate, gradual decline	7.86 (6.41-10)
	High, rise then decline	16 (13.67-18.5)	High, rise then decline	14 (13-17.71)	High, rise then decline	18.02 (16.25-20.33)	High, rise then decline	15.57 (13.43-18.43)

Abbreviations: B2, breast development tanner II; PH2, pubic hair development tanner II; AH2, axillary hair development tanner II.

Supplementary Table 12. The average value of the total score and the 5 components score of psychosocial stress by trajectories for each pubertal outcome of boys

Psychosocial stress	T2 (N=577)		FS (N=652)		P2 (N=658)		A2 (N=684)	
	Trajectory group	Average value						
Total	All	21.2 (11.71-34.33)	All	19.86 (11.29-32.76)	All	20.31 (11.29-34)	All	20 (11.29-32.76)
	Low, gradual decline	13.78 (8.17-19.62)	Low, gradual decline	12.73 (8.07-17.93)	Low, gradual decline	12.67 (7.8-18)	Low, gradual decline	12.43 (8-17.43)
	Moderate, gradual decline	35 (30.33-41.43)	Moderate, gradual decline	33.25 (28.71-37.86)	Moderate, gradual decline	34.24 (28.57-39.08)	Moderate, gradual decline	32.57 (27.57-37.14)
	High, gradual rise	58.55 (53.79-66.5)	High, stable	54.43 (50.83-63)	High, stable	56.24 (51.57-63.13)	High, stable	55.46 (51-62)
Family life	All	6.83 (3.4-12.25)	All	6.43 (3.2-11.85)	All	6.54 (3.33-11.71)	All	6.43 (3.29-11.69)
	Low, gradual decline	4.14 (2-6.2)	Low, gradual decline	4 (2-6)	Low, gradual decline	4 (2-6.14)	Low, gradual decline	3.71 (2-5.71)
	Moderate, gradual decline	12.57 (10.69-15.14)	Moderate, gradual decline	12.25 (9.83-14.43)	Moderate, gradual decline	12.29 (10.2-15.17)	Moderate, gradual decline	11.71 (9.43-14)
	High, rise then decline	21.68 (19.71-26.14)	High, rise then decline	20.86 (19.2-24.43)	High, rise then decline	21.14 (19.71-24.43)	High, rise then decline	20.71 (19-22.29)
Teacher-students relationship	All	1.43 (0.43-3)	All	1.43 (0.5-3)	All	1.43 (0.5-2.86)	All	1.43 (0.57-3)
	Low, gradual decline	0.33 (0-0.71)	Low, gradual decline	0.29 (0-0.71)	Low, gradual decline	0.33 (0-0.71)	Low, gradual decline	0.4 (0.14-0.8)
	Moderate, stable	2.29 (1.6-3.4)	Moderate, stable	2.29 (1.5-3.17)	Moderate, stable	2.17 (1.5-3.29)	Moderate, stable	2.43 (1.57-3.4)
	High, rise then decline	8 (6.86-9.33)	High, rise then decline	7 (6.43-9.14)	High, rise then decline	7.5 (6.57-8.71)	High, rise then decline	7.55 (6.57-9.14)
Academic adaptation	All	3.29 (1.4-5.57)	All	3.14 (1.43-5.43)	All	3.14 (1.43-5.43)	All	3.17 (1.57-5.43)
	Low, gradual decline	0.83 (0.14-1.29)	Low, gradual decline	0.71 (0.14-1.14)	Low, gradual decline	0.86 (0.14-1.29)	Low, gradual decline	0.86 (0.14-1.29)
	Moderate, stable	4 (3-5.43)	Moderate, stable	3.71 (2.67-5.14)	Moderate, stable	3.86 (2.75-5.25)	Moderate, stable	3.71 (2.69-5.22)
	High, rise and decline	10.14 (8.76-11.83)	High, rise and decline	9 (8.29-11)	High, rise and decline	9.62 (8.67-11.29)	High, rise and decline	9.33 (8.29-11.14)
Peer relationship	All	2.67 (1-4.67)	All	2.37 (1-4.5)	All	2.57 (1-4.6)	All	2.43 (1-4.43)
	Low, gradual decline	0.71 (0.29-1.4)	Low, gradual decline	0.67 (0.29-1.14)	Low, gradual decline	0.71 (0.29-1.29)	Low, gradual decline	0.57 (0.29-1.14)
	Moderate, gradual decline	3.67 (2.71-5)	Moderate, gradual decline	3.43 (2.5-4.67)	Moderate, gradual decline	3.86 (2.75-5)	Moderate, gradual decline	3.29 (2.43-4.57)
	High, rise then decline	9.5 (8.21-10.63)	High, rise then decline	8.43 (7.29-10.57)	High, rise then decline	9.46 (8.21-11)	High, rise then decline	8.5 (7.29-10.43)
Life adaptation	All	6.5 (3.33-10)	All	5.67 (3.14-9)	All	5.59 (3.25-9.17)	All	5.43 (3-8.43)
	Low, gradual decline	0.82 (0.21-1.27)	Low, gradual decline	2.59 (1.71-3.67)	Low, gradual decline	3.8 (2.15-5)	Low, gradual decline	3 (1.86-4.43)
	Moderate, gradual decline	6.4 (4-8.5)	Moderate, gradual decline	7.27 (6-9.4)	Moderate, gradual decline	9.85 (7.59-12)	Moderate, gradual decline	7.86 (6.41-10)
	High, rise then decline	16 (13.67-18.5)	High, rise then decline	14 (13-17.71)	High, rise then decline	18.02 (16.25-20.33)	High, rise then decline	15.57 (13.43-18.43)

Abbreviations: Tvol4, testicular volume ≥ 4 ml; FS, first spermatorrhea; PH2, pubic hair development tanner II.

Supplementary Table 13. Hazard ratio of pubertal outcomes of girls associated with psychosocial stress trajectories in unadjusted model and age and BMI adjusted model^a

Psychosocial stress	Model	Trajectory group	B2 (n=438)	Menarche (n=678)	PH2 (n=662)	AH2 (n=681)
			HR (95 % CI)	HR (95 % CI)	HR (95 % CI)	HR (95 % CI)
Total stress	1	Low, gradual decline	ref	ref	ref	ref
		Moderate, gradual decline	0.970 (0.791 - 1.188)	0.875 (0.731 - 1.049)	0.823 (0.691 - 0.979)	0.801 (0.663 - 0.967)
		High, rise then decline	1.070 (0.724 - 1.581)	1.048 (0.804 - 1.366)	1.129 (0.856 - 1.489)	0.945 (0.711 - 1.256)
	2	Low, gradual decline	ref	ref	ref	ref
		Moderate, gradual decline	0.966 (0.789 - 1.184)	0.872 (0.728 - 1.045)	0.738 (0.618 - 0.881)	0.807 (0.667 - 0.977)
		High, rise then decline	1.038 (0.701 - 1.538)	1.051 (0.805 - 1.372)	1.072 (0.812 - 1.415)	0.876 (0.658 - 1.166)
Family life	1	Low, gradual decline	ref	ref	ref	ref
		Moderate, gradual decline	0.925 (0.755 - 1.134)	0.963 (0.783 - 1.185)	0.925 (0.771 - 1.109)	0.806 (0.650 - 1.000)
		High, rise then decline	0.941 (0.675 - 1.310)	0.912 (0.706 - 1.176)	0.884 (0.686 - 1.140)	0.761 (0.583 - 0.995)
	2	Low, gradual decline	ref	ref	ref	ref
		Moderate, gradual decline	0.894 (0.728 - 1.097)	0.994 (0.806 - 1.226)	0.850 (0.708 - 1.021)	0.835 (0.673 - 1.037)
		High, rise then decline	0.974 (0.698 - 1.360)	0.903 (0.697 - 1.170)	0.930 (0.720 - 1.201)	0.781 (0.596 - 1.022)
Teacher-students relationship	1	Low, gradual decline	ref	ref	ref	ref
		Moderate, stable	1.008 (0.826 - 1.229)	0.986 (0.828 - 1.174)	0.929 (0.783 - 1.102)	0.821 (0.682 - 0.988)
		High, rise then decline	1.099 (0.715 - 1.689)	1.208 (0.889 - 1.643)	1.158 (0.833 - 1.611)	1.265 (0.937 - 1.708)
	2	Low, gradual decline	ref	ref	ref	ref
		Moderate, stable	0.978 (0.801 - 1.193)	0.997 (0.836 - 1.189)	0.870 (0.732 - 1.033)	0.828 (0.686 - 0.999)
		High, rise then decline	0.988 (0.641 - 1.523)	1.064 (0.780 - 1.450)	0.850 (0.609 - 1.187)	1.162 (0.859 - 1.571)
Academic adaptation	1	Low, gradual decline	ref	ref	ref	ref
		Moderate, stable	1.139 (0.919 - 1.412)	1.130 (0.932 - 1.371)	1.081 (0.896 - 1.304)	0.975 (0.802 - 1.187)
		High, rise then decline	1.094 (0.797 - 1.502)	1.240 (0.965 - 1.592)	1.257 (0.980 - 1.612)	1.106 (0.854 - 1.432)
	2	Low, gradual decline	ref	ref	ref	ref
		Moderate, stable	1.077 (0.868 - 1.336)	1.041 (0.856 - 1.265)	0.989 (0.819 - 1.194)	0.874 (0.717 - 1.066)
		High, rise then decline	0.909 (0.658 - 1.258)	0.937 (0.726 - 1.209)	0.838 (0.647 - 1.086)	0.872 (0.670 - 1.136)
Peer relationship	1	Low, gradual decline	ref	ref	ref	ref
		Moderate, gradual decline	1.095 (0.870 - 1.379)	0.973 (0.813 - 1.164)	0.965 (0.806 - 1.156)	0.863 (0.715 - 1.041)
		High, rise then decline	0.923 (0.636 - 1.340)	1.061 (0.792 - 1.423)	1.019 (0.765 - 1.358)	0.917 (0.671 - 1.253)
	2	Low, gradual decline	ref	ref	ref	ref
		Moderate, gradual decline	0.995 (0.789 - 1.255)	1.124 (0.939 - 1.346)	1.046 (0.873 - 1.253)	0.978 (0.809 - 1.182)
		High, rise then decline	0.845 (0.582 - 1.228)	1.129 (0.840 - 1.517)	0.988 (0.740 - 1.319)	0.925 (0.676 - 1.264)
Life adaptation	1	Low, gradual decline	ref	ref	ref	ref
		Moderate, gradual decline	1.394 (0.988 - 1.967)	0.935 (0.780 - 1.119)	0.941 (0.796 - 1.113)	0.891 (0.742 - 1.070)
		High, rise then decline	1.367 (0.900 - 2.075)	0.996 (0.765 - 1.297)	0.970 (0.650 - 1.447)	0.984 (0.717 - 1.351)
	2	Low, gradual decline	ref	ref	ref	ref
		Moderate, gradual decline	1.241 (0.878 - 1.754)	1.042 (0.869 - 1.249)	0.954 (0.806 - 1.129)	0.938 (0.780 - 1.128)
		High, rise then decline	1.254 (0.826 - 1.906)	1.084 (0.831 - 1.413)	0.841 (0.562 - 1.260)	0.954 (0.694 - 1.311)

^a Model 1 was unadjusted model. Model 2 adjusted for age at survey 1 and BMI at survey 1. “Low” trajectory group of psychosocial stress was considered as reference.

Abbreviations: B2, breast development tanner II, PH2, pubic hair development tanner II, AH2, axillary hair development tanner II.

Supplementary Table 14. Hazard ratio of pubertal outcomes of boys associated with psychosocial stress trajectories in unadjusted model and age and BMI adjusted model^a

Psychosocial stress	Model	Trajectory group	Tvol4 (n=568)	FS (n=641)	PH2 (n=647)	AH2 (n=672)
			HR (95 % CI)			
Total stress	Model 1	Low, gradual decline	ref	ref	ref	ref
		Moderate, gradual decline	0.890 (0.731 - 1.083)	0.844 (0.684 - 1.041)	0.845 (0.697 - 1.025)	0.900 (0.730 - 1.111)
		High, gradual rise/stable ^b	1.014 (0.714 - 1.440)	0.970 (0.685 - 1.374)	0.802 (0.579 - 1.111)	0.843 (0.589 - 1.207)
	Model 2	Low, gradual decline	ref	ref	ref	ref
		Moderate, gradual decline	1.013 (0.831 - 1.236)	0.931 (0.752 - 1.152)	1.005 (0.826 - 1.223)	0.963 (0.780 - 1.189)
		High, gradual rise/stable ^b	1.157 (0.814 - 1.644)	1.065 (0.750 - 1.512)	0.897 (0.646 - 1.246)	0.750 (0.521 - 1.082)
Family life	Model 1	Low, gradual decline	ref	ref	ref	ref
		Moderate, gradual decline	0.797 (0.656 - 0.968)	0.890 (0.726 - 1.091)	0.785 (0.651 - 0.947)	0.837 (0.680 - 1.029)
		High, rise then decline	0.773 (0.528 - 1.132)	0.736 (0.495 - 1.094)	0.710 (0.479 - 1.052)	0.857 (0.583 - 1.259)
	Model 2	Low, gradual decline	ref	ref	ref	ref
		Moderate, gradual decline	0.905 (0.743 - 1.102)	1.008 (0.819 - 1.241)	0.876 (0.724 - 1.059)	0.909 (0.736 - 1.122)
		High, rise then decline	0.988 (0.672 - 1.452)	0.850 (0.570 - 1.268)	0.829 (0.558 - 1.232)	0.789 (0.534 - 1.167)
Teacher-students relationship	Model 1	Low, gradual decline	ref	ref	ref	ref
		Moderate, stable	0.921 (0.763 - 1.110)	1.069 (0.876 - 1.303)	1.067 (0.887 - 1.283)	0.963 (0.787 - 1.179)
		High, rise then decline	0.935 (0.666 - 1.312)	0.901 (0.623 - 1.302)	0.941 (0.671 - 1.318)	1.038 (0.715 - 1.509)
	Model 2	Low, gradual decline	ref	ref	ref	ref
		Moderate, stable	0.889 (0.736 - 1.073)	0.984 (0.806 - 1.201)	1.029 (0.854 - 1.239)	0.944 (0.769 - 1.158)
		High, rise then decline	1.035 (0.737 - 1.455)	1.010 (0.697 - 1.462)	1.012 (0.721 - 1.420)	0.849 (0.578 - 1.248)
Academic adaptation	Model 1	Low, gradual decline	ref	ref	ref	ref
		Moderate, stable	1.032 (0.844 - 1.261)	0.927 (0.749 - 1.146)	0.954 (0.786 - 1.157)	0.971 (0.782 - 1.206)
		High, rise then decline	1.133 (0.834 - 1.539)	1.120 (0.829 - 1.513)	1.038 (0.779 - 1.384)	0.992 (0.714 - 1.377)
	Model 2	Low, gradual decline	ref	ref	ref	ref
		Moderate, stable	0.925 (0.755 - 1.134)	0.766 (0.615 - 0.955)	0.879 (0.721 - 1.072)	0.900 (0.722 - 1.122)
		High, rise then decline	1.140 (0.838 - 1.550)	0.867 (0.639 - 1.176)	0.841 (0.628 - 1.127)	0.664 (0.473 - 0.933)
Peer relationship	Model 1	Low, gradual decline	ref	ref	ref	ref
		Moderate, gradual decline	1.177 (0.973 - 1.423)	0.864 (0.708 - 1.056)	0.982 (0.818 - 1.179)	0.885 (0.721 - 1.086)
		High, rise then decline	0.853 (0.612 - 1.189)	0.785 (0.571 - 1.080)	0.758 (0.546 - 1.052)	0.762 (0.548 - 1.061)
	Model 2	Low, gradual decline	ref	ref	ref	ref
		Moderate, gradual decline	1.304 (1.075 - 1.582)	0.881 (0.720 - 1.078)	0.959 (0.797 - 1.154)	0.857 (0.697 - 1.054)
		High, rise then decline	1.201 (0.857 - 1.683)	0.908 (0.658 - 1.253)	0.866 (0.623 - 1.203)	0.716 (0.513 - 0.999)
Life adaptation	Model 1	Low, gradual decline	ref	ref	ref	ref
		Moderate, gradual decline	0.819 (0.678 - 0.988)	0.796 (0.651 - 0.973)	0.756 (0.628 - 0.910)	0.814 (0.664 - 0.998)
		High, rise then decline	0.752 (0.528 - 1.071)	0.746 (0.514 - 1.084)	0.634 (0.450 - 0.893)	0.636 (0.445 - 0.908)
	Model 2	Low, gradual decline	ref	ref	ref	ref
		Moderate, gradual decline	0.946 (0.779 - 1.149)	0.981 (0.796 - 1.209)	0.928 (0.765 - 1.125)	0.920 (0.747 - 1.133)
		High, rise then decline	0.894 (0.626 - 1.276)	0.864 (0.593 - 1.260)	0.764 (0.541 - 1.080)	0.643 (0.448 - 0.923)

^a Model 1 was unadjusted model. Model 2 adjusted for age at survey 1 and BMI at survey 1. “Low” trajectory group of psychosocial stress was considered as reference.

^b “High, gradual rise” for Tvol4 observation, “High, stable” for the other 3 pubertal outcomes.

Abbreviations: Tvol4, testicular volume ≥ 4 ml, FS, first spermatorrhea, PH2, pubic hair development tanner II, AH2, axillary hair development tanner II.

Supplementary Figure 1. Flow chart of study process

Supplementary Figure 2. Directed acyclic graph of the relationship between Psychosocial stress and pubertal outcomes for girls and boys^a.

^a Light grey nodes: variables associated with both exposure and outcomes (confounders); Dark grey nodes: variables associated with exposure and/or potential mediators. Black nodes: variables associated with the outcome and/or potential mediators.

Abbreviations: BMI, Body mass index.

Supplementary Figure 3 Trajectory changes of the 5 components score of psychosocial stress for girls

Abbreviations: B2, breast development tanner II; PH2, pubic hair development tanner II; AH2, axillary hair development tanner II.

Supplementary Figure 4 Trajectory changes of the 5 components score of psychosocial stress for boys

Abbreviations: Tvol4, testicular volume ≥ 4 ml; FS, first spermatorrhea; PH2, pubic hair development tanner II.

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